

Research

Human Trafficking from Bangladesh to Malaysia: A Preliminary Study

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Abstract: Nowadays, human trafficking has become a great concern for Bangladesh. Internationally, human trafficking is considered as a much growing crime. But in the regional context, it has become a lucrative business for trafficking networks. Every year thousands of Bangladeshis are migrating overseas either legally or by illegal means. In the last couples of year, total flow of remittance was not satisfactory because of the diplomatic tension between the Bangladesh and major migrants receiving countries. In addition, the new migrations policies of the Middle-Eastern countries also have shrunk the scope for Bangladeshi migrants. As a result, the number of human trafficking from Bangladesh to Malaysia has increased. There are various causes of human trafficking which are relies on the socio-economic circumstances of Bangladesh. Some of the causes of trafficking have deep connection with international network. The purpose of this paper is to unveil the key causes of human trafficking by analyzing the field data with focusing on the theoretical perspectives of the migration. It also argues for effective mechanism to monitor the whole process of human trafficking from Bangladesh to Malaysia in an urgent basis.

Keywords: Human Trafficking, Hidden population, Anti-trafficking policy, Traffickers, Migration theory

1. Introduction

In October 2014, the police authorities of Thailand rescued about 134 Bangladeshi illegal migrants from the jungles of Southern Thailand. They were going to Malaysia by illegal means. The horrific sufferings of these workers remind the slave trade of the middle age. These people had to eat leaves (tree) for a week to survive in the remote forest of Thailand. Most of them left their home for Malaysia to get rid of the poverty (The Daily Star, 2014). Aforementioned story delineates the magnitude of trafficking problem in Bangladesh. Moreover, Bangladesh land area covers 147,570 sq. km. with eight largest population of the world (BBS, 2019). In 2019, its total

population stood at 163 million (United Nation, 2019). Population density, natural disaster, poverty, illiteracy, lack of employment opportunities are several causes that compel people to search a better employment opportunities in foreign countries. Migration has been a livelihood strategy of Bangladeshis for long time. Practically, international migration takes place within the legal framework between the sending and receiving states. But every year significant number of people has crossed the national border illegally for livelihoods. The main destination countries for Bangladeshi migrants are India, Malaysia and Middle East. The traffickers use the Bay of Bengal as a transit route to migrate Malaysia illegally. The fishing season from October to January is the high time for human trafficking. Local brokers from Bangladesh, pirates from Andaman, collaborators from Thailand and traffickers from Myanmar are involved in this human trafficking process. Trafficking of unskilled labor force from Bangladesh to Malaysia through the Bay of Bengal adds new dimension in the trafficking history of the continent of Asia. And it is also one of the perilous routes of human trafficking of the world. Many of the trafficking victims have lost their lives in the boat because of the torture and hazardous condition. Most of the victims are from the non-traditional migrant prone areas of the country. These are mainly form low international labor migration producing districts: Jessore, Khulna, Bagerhat, Sirajgunj, Rangpur, Dinajpur, Brahmanbaria, Pabna and the Cox's Bazar (Siddique, 2014). The main objective of this paper is to unpack the basic causes of human trafficking from Bangladesh to Malaysia only by using the Bay of Bengal as a maritime transit. And it will endeavor to shed light on what policies government should take to ease the problem. It will assess the theoretical perspective based on the secondary data. This paper has framed the following questions; what are the main causes of human trafficking? Why do traffickers choose Malaysia as a destination country through the maritime route of Bay of Bengal? What measures Bangladesh government need to take for tackling the human trafficking?

2. Methodology

For the purpose of the paper secondary sources; reports and publications of various organizations, journals, booklets, newsletters, photographs, and newspaper clippings have been assessed. Secondary data was collected from many organizations like, DHAKA AHASANIA MISSION, Bangladesh National Women Lawyers Association (BNWLA), International Organization for Migration (IOM), The International Centre for Diarrhea Disease Research,

Bangladesh (ICDDR, B,) and Local Government Bodies, Chittagong Metropolitan Police Headquarters' information cell, Refugee and Migratory Movement Research Unit (RMMRU), Young Power in Social Action (YPSA), Winlock International, International Labor Organization (ILO), Ministry of Women and Children Affairs, Ministry of Law and many others. Primary source is based on the interview and case study. Questionnaire is covered through open and close ended questions. The sample size of the research is 40 that include 20 victims and 20 victim's family members. Due to the hidden nature of the trafficking victims (Heckathorn, 1997), 30 respondents are taken for the interviews where 23 are the members of the victim's family and 7 are the victims.

3. Concept of Human Trafficking

Human trafficking takes place for two purposes: trafficking for sex work and trafficking for forced slavery, or indentured labor. Most of the researches on the human trafficking are based on the women and children (Aronowitz, 2009; Mahdavi, 2011; Bohl, 2010). Existing literatures focus less on the human trafficking of men for the purpose of exploitation of labor and selling them to the industry owner. Various involving organizations include voluntary and facilitated migration, exploitation of the labor, and prostitution in the definition of the human trafficking (RUHI, 2003:45). The historical experience of human trafficking has changed over time because of the changing realities. Nonetheless trafficking researchers also disagree on how the definition of trafficking should be defined and studied. International migratory movement prescribed some of the pre-conditions of the human trafficking (IOM, 2005:10):

- Money (or another form of payment) changes hands.
- A facilitator the trafficker is involved.
- An international border is crossed.
- Entry is illegal.
- The movement is voluntary.

There is a complex relation among the three terms migration, smuggling and trafficking. Those terms are confused in some extend for the trafficking researchers. All of them are called as irregular migration by some researchers. Irregular migration includes people who enter a country without the proper authority, for example, by entering without passing through a border control or entering with fraudulent documents. It also the people who have entered a country legally but

after expire of the visa he/she terms as an irregular migrants. The term also comprehends people moved by migrant smugglers or human traffickers, and those who deliberately abuse the asylum system. (Khalid Koser, 2007: 55-56). Both the victims of smuggling and trafficking leave a country willingly. And they are exploited by the agents. The noticeable difference between the trafficking victim and smuggled persons is that smuggled persons enjoy the rights of free movement. On the other hand, trafficking victims have to stay in a locked room or firms.

4. Major Findings

The main objective of this paper is to find out the causes of the trafficking and what types of policies should need to prioritize for protecting the human trafficking problem. To fulfill the purpose 30 respondents were selected purposively from the four Upzila of Cox’s Bazar, Rangamati, Brahmanbaria and Chittagong districts. In the subsequent sections the survey results will be analyzed. Respondents were asked about the demographic information, causes and measures to curb the human trafficking.

Figure 1: Sample Area of the Population

Source: Field work 2014

4.1 Age of the Respondents

The graphical presentation of the age distribution of the sample is presented in Table 1. The majority of the respondents (Victim; n = 4 or 57% and victim Family member; n = 8 or 34%) fall in the age category below 30 and 51 and more. This is followed by 1 (14%) of the Victim and 6 (26%) victim’s family member of the total respondents in the age category 31-35 years. The age category 36-40 years old, constitutes 14% (n = 1) victim and 4% (n = 1) victim’s family member

of the sample. In the age category of 46-50 there is 14% victim (n=1) and victim family member constitute 13% (n=3).

Table 1: Ages of the Respondents

Age	Victim		Victim's Family member	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Below 30	4	57.14	3	13.04
31-35	1	14.28	6	26.08
36-40	1	14.28	1	4.34
41-45	0	0	2	8.69
46-50	1	14.28	3	13.04
Above 51	0	0	8	34.78
Total	7	100	23	100

Source: Field work 2014

The older age above 51 has no representation of victim. From the ensuing results it can therefore be concluded that the majority of the victim participating in the study is fairly young, ranging below 30. And majority of the victim's family members are above 51 by covering the 35%.

4.2 Educational Qualifications

Table 2 illustrates the education level of the sample. It depicts that the majority of the respondents, 42% (n = 3) victim and 65% (n = 15) victim family member respondents are illiterate, while 14% (n = 1) victim and 21% (n = 5) victim family member respondents completed primary level and 14% (n=1) victim and 13% (n=3) victim family member possess only the junior school certificate. 28% (n = 1) of victim respondents has a SSC degree. So, it can be easily conceived that rate of illiteracy is influential factor in the decision making of the illegal migration.

Table 2: Educational Qualifications of the Respondents

Educational Background	Victim		Victim's Family Member	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Illiterate	3	42.85	15	65.21
Primary	1	14.28	5	21.73
JSC	1	14.28	3	13.04
SSC	1	14.28	0	0
HSC	1	14.28	0	0
BA/BSS/BBA/BSc	0	0	0	0
Others	0	0	0	0
Total	7	100	23	100

Source: Field work 2014

4.3 Occupations of the Respondents

Profession of trafficking victim is an important variable to determine the root causes of human trafficking. In the profession chart of victim majority of the victims are farmer 57% (n=4) and remaining percentage are from the student, driver and day laborer.

On the other hand, majority of the profession of the victim's family members are 57% (n=12) farmer. House wife and driver are represent 14% (n=3). And other remaining professions are domestic worker, day laborer and shop keeper. The major finding is that most of the lower income family members are the main victim of the human trafficking.

4.4 Network of Trafficking

Network and system theory is the prominent and emerging theoretical approach for analyzing the causes of human trafficking from Bangladesh to Malaysia. The importance of networks for migration can hardly be overstated (they) rank amongst the most important explanatory factors for migration (Arango, 2004: 28). Boyd and Nowak (2012: 79-83) mention the three types of networks; these are family and personal networks, labour network, and illegal migrant networks. Besides Samers (2010: 87-93) draws attention to the middle way of migration networking by focusing on the smuggling and trafficking of human beings for the purpose of the exploitation of

labor, sexual slavery. Following chart indicates the highest number of respondents are the victim of illegal migrants networks of brokers 67% (n=20) and followed by the 13% (n=4) of the personal network of friend. The network of kinship 3% (n=1) and relative 7% (n=2) also represent the personal and social network. There are 10% (n=3) of respondents mentioned the network of others means which are mainly related with the labour network of the human trafficking victims. These types of network are grown in the work place or in the mean time of the labour relations among the workers.

Figure 2: Network of Trafficking

4.5 Causes of Human Trafficking

It is important to bear in mind that majority of the causes of human trafficking are the direct results of poverty. Poverty is considered to be the major reason behind the decision making of illegal migration from Bangladesh to Malaysia through the route of dangerous and risky the Bay of Bengal. These poverty-stricken people are the victim of trafficking because they have a few options for earning their livelihood. It is also noticeable that the poor can easily be exploited by the illegal human trafficking network in various phases of life because of their vulnerability. In the following chart there are 50% (n=15) of the respondents mention poverty is the causes of human trafficking. Lack of employment opportunities is another cause of human trafficking according to the answer of the respondents. Around 13% (n=3) of human trafficking victim responses that lack of employment compel them to take the challenging decision to migrate Malaysia through informal channel. An exceptional finding of this research is that around 17%

(n=4) of the respondents mention the shutdown of visa in Middle Eastern countries is one of the causes of the human trafficking. During my field work one of the victim's father noted that when they failed to get the visa of Middle Eastern states, they took the decision to send their son to Malaysia through illegal route.

Figure 3: Causes of Human Trafficking

5. Data interpretation in light of existing theories

New classical migration theories are centered on the push and pull mechanism. Respondents shared the presence of various causes and theoretical linkage with migration. Most of the respondents of the Dailpadha village at Ukhia in Cox's Bazar noted that network theory plays very prominent role in taking the decision to migrate Malaysia. Network has a spill over impact into irregular migration. Badsha Mia (65) father of trafficked victim told that young generation is the main target of the trafficking networks. On the other hand, one of the women of the same village informed that the available information is the premier factor in the decision making of her husband's migration to Malaysia. Globalization has enhanced the rate of migration all over the world. Traffickers allured the poverty stricken and illiterate people to agree with their proposal. Everyone irrespective of their age, educational qualifications and economic capabilities knows about the life style of the foreign countries through the satellite and news media. Even we cannot ignore the social gossip in the tea stall and other gathering places for the unhindered flow of

information. Ridwan (25) one of the unfortunate returned migrants of the Janglakhata of the Chakaria upzila of Cox's Bazar narrated that he was influenced by the personal network approach of the Boyd & Nowak (2012) before going to the Malaysia. Samers (2010) revealed that traffickers and smugglers used to take the benefit of the social and business networks in recruiting the cheap labor from the third world countries like Bangladesh through deception. Network is considered a reliable means for the smuggling and trafficking agents in Bangladesh for exploiting the migrants. Saskia Sassen (1988) argues that global cities of the developed countries help to amplify the migrations flow from the third world countries. There are prominent discourses in Malaysian society that the lower and dangerous jobs are for the illegal migrants. M. J. Piore (1979) argues that developed and industrialist countries follow the dual approaches for the rapid growth in the industrial sectors by encouraging the illegal migration. In Malaysia the smugglers agent continuously exploit the migrants by forced labor, slavery and restriction on the movement. Majority of the respondents informed that world system theory (Wallerstein, 1974) and network theory were the notable agents in the decision making process.

6. Policy Implications

The priorities of the Government of Bangladesh (GOB) should be very specific for the anti-human trafficking sectors. The affirmative action like negotiation with the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA) and United Arab Emirates (UAE) can solve the problem of human trafficking in the short term and long run. Moreover, the generation of new jobs for the unemployment youths also poses a great challenge to the Bangladesh government. In 2013, the most notable achievement of the government was the enactment of the Overseas Employment and Migrant Workers Law 2013. This has been an inclusive law which involved all relevant stakeholders. It was enacted in the National Parliament on 23 October 2013. This law has 9 chapters and 49 sections. For the first time this law has endorsed migrants and their families to lodge criminal case against any deception and civil case for seeking compensation. This is a big achievement for migrant workers. However, despite the demands of civil society, the government did not pay heed to include ILO Convention 97 (revised 1949), Migrant Workers Convention 143 and Equality of Opportunities and Treatment towards Migrants Workers Convention 1975 in its preamble. Of course it mentioned UN Convention on Rights of All Migrants' Workers and members of their families, 1990 (Siddiqui, 2014).

In order to establish rights of migrants' workers who are the victim of trafficking, following recommendations must be taken account by the policy makers.

- Bangladesh government should raise the issue in the regional and international forum for a durable solution.
- The case of the human trafficking should be run under the special tribunal.
- As most of the human trafficking activities have been occurred remote areas of Cox's Bazar mainly coastal areas. So, to curb the brokers as well as middle men in the trafficking process additional police investigation centres be formed in those area including the coordination from the other forces.
- Bangladesh has around 80 km river border with Myanmar. For curbing the illegal flow of Rohingya as well as the human trafficking government should also put more emphasize to control the matter by using security forces.
- Anti-trafficking committee in the Ward level should be formed in the coastal areas of Cox's Bazar and Chittagong by including the Upazilla Nirbahi Officer (UNO), Officer in search of Thana (TNO), Chairman, members, respectful individuals, and officers of the NGO from the respective Union. District committee will monitor all of the issues related with human trafficking.
- Finally, Bangladesh and Malaysia must work together in a sincere atmosphere to solve the problem in a realistic and humanitarian ground keeping in mind.

Implementation of these recommendations is a big challenge to the Bangladesh government. The role of Malaysia as a receiving country in curbing the human trafficking is also crucial.

7. Conclusion

Human trafficking is indeed a grim conundrum for Bangladesh. Every day hundreds of young working forces of Bangladesh are trying to cross the Bay of Bengal with a destination to reach Malaysia for a better life. During the field work in the Cox's Bazar sadar, Ukia Upzilla of Cox's Bazar and Rangamati district the multi-dimensional causes of the human trafficking were found. In recent days the progress of the economy of Bangladesh has been waned because of the unequal distribution of resources to the small portions of the elite of the society. Illiteracy is the main cause of human trafficking. There are other causes like; poverty, lack of employment opportunities, non-availability of social security, allurements of providing posh job in Malaysia,

etc. Newspaper report claimed that most of victims of the human traffickers in the route of Bay of Bengal are from the new areas where the proportions of the migration are very low. After failing to get working visa in major migrants receiving countries, they decided to go Malaysia through the risky path of the Bay of Bengal. But by knowing all the suffering in the boats they decided to accept the precarious path of irregular migration because of their long time disappointment in Bangladesh in terms of income generation and economic opportunities. The core problem of human trafficking from Bangladesh to Malaysia through the Bay of Bengal lies in the ineffectiveness and fragile economic policies of the GOB. Moreover, there are a number of steps immediately be taken to handle this problem. First, Government has to implement the recent human trafficking related laws of 2012 and 2013 for tackling the human trafficking menace immediately. Second, government must prioritize to open the labor market of UAE and other countries of the Middle East. Third, GOB should search for new countries for sending labour forces. In addition, there must be a permanent migration policy in the foreign policy of Bangladesh so that it will be ensured their rights. Last but not least, all the involving stakeholders in Bangladesh should keep in mind that they are the oxygen of the economy of Bangladesh.

References

- Arango, J. (2004). Theories of International Migration, In D. Joly (ed.), *International Migration and the New Millennium*. Aldershot: Ashgate, 15-36.
- Aronowitz, A. A. (2009). *Human Trafficking and Human Misery: The global trade in human begins*. Westport: Praeger Publishers.
- Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics (2019), *Statistical Year Book*. Retrieved from <https://bbs.portal.gov.bd/site/page/b0b261bd-e68f-4897-9339-517096f38262>. Accessed 25 May,2020.
- Boyd, M, and Nowak, J, (2012). Social Networks and International Migration, in Martiniello, M, and Rath, J. (eds.). *An Introduction to International Migration Studies*, Amsterdam: Amsterdam University Press, 77-103.
- Bohl, K. (2010). *Human trafficking as a livelihood strategy? - A case study of trafficking in women and children from Nepal to India*. Master's Thesis, Aolbrong University.
- Daily Star (19 October, 2014). *Modern-Day slave trade unearthed*. The Daily Star. Retrieved from <https://www.thedailystar.net/modern-day-slave-trade-unearthed-46333>
- Koser, K. (2007). *International Migration: A Very Short Introduction*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Heckathorn, D.D. (1997). Respondent-driven sampling: a new approach to the study of hidden populations, in *Social Problems*, 44(2): 174-198.

Laczko, F. (2005). What is Human Trafficking?, in Frank, L. and Elzbieta, G. (eds.). Data and Research on Human Trafficking: A Global Survey. Offprint of the Special Issue of International Migration Vol. 43 (1/2), IOM.

Mahdavi, P. (2011). Gridlock: labor, migration, and human trafficking in Dubai. California: Stanford University Press.

Piore, M.J. (1979). Birds of Passage: Migrant Labour and Industrial Societies. New York: Cambridge University Press.

RUHI, RUH A. (2003). Human Trafficking in Bangladesh: An Overview. Asian Affairs, Vol. 25, No. Page 45.

Samers, M. (2010). Migration, London: Rutledge.

Sassen, S. (1988). The Mobility of Labor and Capital, New York: Cambridge University Press.

Siddiqui, T. (2014). Irregular Bangladeshi Migrants: where is the Migration Law 2013?, The Daily Star, December 2, 2014, Dhaka..

Wallerstein, I. (1974). The Modern World-System: Capitalist Agriculture and the Origins of the European World-Economy in the Sixteenth Century. New York: Academic Press.

World Population Prospect. (2019) Available at:
https://population.un.org/wpp/Publications/Files/WPP2019_Highlights.pdf.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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